

MORPHOLOGICAL DIVERSITY OF LUNAR COMPLEX CRATER CENTRAL PEAKS: RESULTS FROM GLOBAL SURVEY Roshan A. Shukla and Deepak Dhingra, Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India – 208016 (roshanadarshshukla@gmail.com, deepdpes@gmail.com)

Introduction: Central peaks of complex craters are the mountain-like geomorphological unit found in the central part of the crater floor. They expose deep crustal materials making them invaluable windows into the subsurface lithological composition [1]. Because the Moon has no wind or flowing water, it doesn't experience erosion the way many other planetary bodies do. This results in relatively better preservation of central peak features which, along with presence of a large number of craters, makes the Moon an ideal location for our study.

Motivation and Major objectives: Prior investigations [2,3,4] have measured central peak attributes (heights, area, volume) as functions of the crater diameter. However, the linkage of the target properties, size of the crater and pre-impact topography to the morphological variations of the central peaks is still a knowledge gap. We are addressing this through a systematic survey of the complex craters on the Moon. Our primary objective is to rigorously characterize central peak morphological diversity and investigate the potential morphological controls.

Data and Methods: The initial survey of the lunar surface was done using the Wide-Angle Camera [5] (WAC) aboard the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) by dividing the lunar surface into grids. The craters (>30 km diameter) from the LPI database by Losiak [6] and revised by Öhman [7] have been incorporated for this study. Detailed morphologic and morphometric investigations have been carried out using Kaguya Terrain Camera images [8] (~10m/pixel), LRO Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter (LOLA) [9] (~60m/pixel) and derived products SELENE-LOLA co-registered DEM (SLDEM) in ArcGIS.

Although Copernican and Eratosthenian-aged craters represent only ~5% of the craters >30 km diameter in the database [7], they represent one of better-preserved classes of craters which is critical for geomorphological studies. In this work, we are incorporating ~75% of these craters wherein the peak was not damaged by any prominent impact post formation of the peak. Out of the 90 craters, 11 belong to the Mare regions while remaining are in the Highland terrain.

Emerging Results: Although each peak has individual morphological character, it is possible to classify them into broad morphological classes [3,10]. The global survey shows that central peaks primarily form as a singular peak complex (~95%) while remaining occur as two or more peaks Fig 1. In terms of shape, most peaks are either nearly circular in shape or elliptical. Some peaks are arcuate,

Fig 1. Central peaks of a) Stevinus crater (Dia: ~71.5 km) and b) Hayn crater (Dia: ~86km) are outlined in red and the white boundary represents the entire region of the crater floor

which can be considered as sub-class of linear peaks. We will be presenting the trends from our global study.

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